

Knowledge and Skills of Business Administration Graduates and Their Entrepreneurial Performance

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Abstract:- Graduates' competencies are important factors in influencing entrepreneurial performance and are extremely important for economic growth and development. This study determined the knowledge and skills of Business Administration graduates concerning their entrepreneurial performance. The study used the descriptive-correlational design. The 140 respondents who graduated from the school year 2011 to 2019 from the Business Administration program were selected randomly. Entrepreneurial Knowledge, Skills, and Performance Questionnaires were used in gathering the data as research instruments. Results revealed that the entrepreneurial knowledge, and the entrepreneurial skills of the graduates, are satisfactory while their performance is very good. Results also revealed that graduates' entrepreneurial knowledge and skills influence their entrepreneurial performance. The program outcomes of the Business Administration curriculum were observed in the performance of the graduates as entrepreneurs. The need to develop twenty-first-century entrepreneurial skills to be more competitive and facilitate the graduates' readiness towards entrepreneurship.

Keywords:- *Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Knowledge, Entrepreneurial Performance, Entrepreneurial Skills, Twenty-First-Century Skills.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The value of entrepreneurship has been recognized by the government, the academic community, and researchers (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2016). As a result, politicians, economists, and academics have discussed starting a business and cultivating an entrepreneurial culture. This issue is based on the premise that new businesses contribute to job creation, economic progress, and political and social stability. (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2016; Postigo, Iacobucci & Tamborini, 2018; Wennekers & Thurik, 2019).

Furthermore, entrepreneurship has a positive impact on promoting innovation, creating jobs, increasing productivity, and generating social and economic wealth in a country's economy where promotion is viewed as a national priority by governments all over the world to develop innovative solutions to a specific problem (Wennekers & Thurik, 2019). Moreover, starting and sustaining a business in the digital environment entails using the internet and other virtual networks to conduct electronic trade. Therefore, many entrepreneurs can launch new

companies in various business formats using technical business platforms in the new digital economy (Yaghoubi & Motaghd, 2017).

In line with this, many people believe that entrepreneurial education is an acceptable answer to the fourth industrial revolution, which requires all people and organizations in society to be increasingly equipped with entrepreneurial capabilities in a more complicated world (Aidara et al., 2021). Schools have opened business and entrepreneurship courses for college students to be oriented with the strategic ways of running a business. The primary objective of schools is to teach students to think critically while adapting some theoretical concepts integrated with the course. Students are taught to select a predetermined objective and acquire the methods and resources necessary to achieve its goals effectively (Abun, Foronda, Belandres, Agoot, & Magallanes, 2019).

A crucial component of higher education is developing students' entrepreneurial knowledge and abilities in a global economy (Jackson, 2017). This is especially significant considering recent research findings indicating that while students graduate with discipline-specific knowledge, they lack strength in various areas, including mathematical and literacy abilities, innovation, cultural awareness, and problem-solving skills. If higher education institutions fail to provide students with these abilities, employers, particularly small business owners, will carry the financial responsibility of teaching them through additional training and development, which would necessitate financial investment (Landrieu & Murray, 2017).

Educational institutions play an important role in providing and developing necessary skills and knowledge for all graduates. However, entrepreneurship education is a challenging subject to grasp. The variety of scholars can help understand the intricacy of entrepreneurship education, which can be defined as the study of, preparation for, and practice of entrepreneurship (Kyguolienė & Švipas, 2019). Attempting to provide an understanding of what entrepreneurship is, as well as how to set up and manage a business, falls under the category of entrepreneurship teaching, to provide the necessary knowledge and skills to start and manage a business, as well as organizing the entrepreneurial learning process experientially through entrepreneurship (Lackeus, 2015; Komarkova, Gagliardi, Conrads, & Collado, 2015).

Problem-solving, the creation of tacit knowledge via action, dedication and ideals, and cultural skills are all important 21st-century skills for a successful business (Kole, 2017). Entrepreneurial skills are a subset of these generic skills that improve students' ability to think critically in a real-world business setting while making sound judgments for solving complicated situations. These abilities aid the entrepreneur in developing fresh ideas in novel conditions, exhibiting ingenuity and a willingness to learn from successes and failures (Bedwell et al., 2014; Curtin, 2004; Gibbons-Wood & Lange, 2000; Sin et al., 2016). Entrepreneurs need various knowledge, skills, and talents, including communication and teamwork. These skills include the capacity to work together to solve issues, communicate, and invent new things. However, college graduates lack many abilities (Boyles, 2012).

The perceived entrepreneurial skills among students are an important factor in becoming self-employed, managing their businesses while building confidence in negotiating with others, and collaboratively working while showing perseverance (Galloway, Anderson, Brown, & Wilson, 2016). As a result, academics have attempted to define and evaluate critical entrepreneurial abilities that improve entrepreneurial performance (Wickham, 2016). Given the importance of entrepreneurship in the nation's economy and graduates as a possible source of entrepreneurs, extensive research on entrepreneurship skills and performance is needed. Entrepreneurial skills refer to the individuals' ability to start or transform an enterprise while adding value through the organization of resources and opportunities. They are considered key competencies to promote employability, involving personal initiative, self-learning, and enterprise development (Hirsch et al., 2015).

Another factor to consider is that entrepreneurial skills have been identified as an important aspect of research and practice's dynamic teaching and learning process (Lans, 2018). Thus, entrepreneurship education must provide students with the skills needed to establish a firm, while entrepreneurship learning must support the growth of knowledge necessary for beginning and managing a business (Kakkonen, 2015; Pfeifer and Borozan, 2016; Politis, 2015;). Therefore, entrepreneurship teaching must provide students with a learning foundation to develop entrepreneurial skills (Sánchez, 2016; Sitzmann, 2017).

Entrepreneurial performance is a multi-faceted concept that has been assessed using a range of variables (Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 2017). Growth and profitability are common indicators of a company's financial health, even if they can sometimes produce a trade-off. Firms may spend extensively on long-term growth at the expense of short-term profitability (Zahra, 2016). Sales, earnings, employment, and market share are all indicators of firm growth. In contrast, profitability indicators include accounting-based metrics like return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and return on sales (ROS). Non-financial performance includes a variety of

operational metrics such as technological excellence, competitive capacities, productivity, and export performance (Stam et al., 2015). Non-financial performance can also include the owners' or managers' happiness and overall success rating (Rauch et al., 2019).

In academic institutions, future entrepreneurs are expected to acquire the knowledge they need for their future endeavors. Through formal education, students prepare themselves to become successful practicing entrepreneurs. With the aforementioned literature and studies, the researcher, a college instructor, conducted the study to assess the perceived entrepreneurial knowledge and skills of BSBA graduates regarding their entrepreneurial performance. This study determined the knowledge and skills of Business Administration graduates and their entrepreneurial performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used the descriptive-correlational design. The main goal of descriptive research is to describe the phenomenon and its characteristics. This research mainly focuses on answering "how" rather than "what or why" something has happened. The data may be obtained qualitatively, but it is often analyzed quantitatively, utilizing averages, frequencies, percentages, or other statistical analyses to determine the significant relationship (Nassaji, 2015). Meanwhile, statistical control is frequently used in correlational approaches to filtering out extraneous variables' influence, resulting in more accurate estimates of connections between variables or a conservative test of hypotheses (Becker et al., 2016). The design was considered appropriate for the present study, which determined the perceived knowledge and skills of Business Administration graduates' entrepreneurial performance.

This study was conducted in one of the private institutions in Ozamiz City, Philippines. The institution is situated in Region 10, Misamis Occidental, in the northern part of Mindanao. It is a private, non-sectarian institution of learning. It is recognized by the Philippine Association of Colleges and Universities Commission on Accreditation (PACUCOA) as an institution with many accredited programs. As a result, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) granted the institution an Autonomous Status. The College of Business and Management, one of the tertiary education colleges at Misamis University, offers the Business Administration program that is granted Level III 2nd re-accredited status by the PACUCOA.

The respondents of this study were the selected Business Administration graduates. There were 140 respondents randomly selected as graduates from 2011 to 2019. They are currently practicing entrepreneurship in municipalities and cities in Region 10 and are involved in entrepreneurial activity for not less than a year. They also had given consent to participate. The respondents were asked to rate their entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and performance using the questionnaires used in this study. This study utilized researcher-

made instruments which were validated, pilot tested, and yielded a Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7.

Before the conduct of the study, permission was obtained from the Dean of the Graduate School of Misamis University, Ozamiz City. Similarly, approval was sought from the Misamis University Alumni Office to access the graduates' contact information. After permission was gained, the researcher administered the questionnaires virtually through google forms to the respondents who were purposively selected being Business Administration graduates. Immediate retrieval of the instruments was observed. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents to ensure they were fully informed about the study. The respondents were assured of the confidentiality and privacy of their answers. They were also informed that they could withdraw their participation in the study at any time they wished to.

Mean and Standard Deviation were utilized in assessing the level of the respondents' entrepreneurial knowledge as to starting a business, finance and marketing, and the human resource; the level of the respondents' entrepreneurial skills as to technical skills, management skills, business skills, and personal-entrepreneurial skills; and the level of the respondents' entrepreneurial performance as to financial ratio, business growth, and the comparative business performance.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized in exploring the significant relationship between the entrepreneurial knowledge of graduates and their entrepreneurial performance and the significant relationship between the entrepreneurial skills of graduates and their entrepreneurial performance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Level of the Respondents' Entrepreneurial Knowledge

Table 1 presents the respondents' entrepreneurial knowledge. It is indicated that the entrepreneurial knowledge of the respondents is satisfactory (M=3.17; SD=0.15). Furthermore, all the constructs, such as knowledge of starting their businesses(M=3.00; SD=.35), knowledge of finance and marketing (M=3.24; SD=0.48), and knowledge of human resources (M=3.28; SD=0.45) are described as satisfactory. This means that the respondents have the basic knowledge of engaging in entrepreneurial activities.

The study's finding indicates that knowledge of starting a business is key in determining the concept of innovativeness and technique in making the business more successful. Furthermore, entrepreneurs had adequate financial and marketing knowledge when they started their businesses, and they have been able to make appropriate marketing programs for their financial projections to become more realistic and attainable. Furthermore, the study's findings revealed that the respondents are knowledgeable in managing their human

resources since human capital is the backbone of a successful business.

The study's findings coincide with the claim of Tittel and Terzidis (2020) that the central focus of entrepreneurship is to let the entrepreneurs acquire knowledge and skills before the conduct of the actual business because it determines the initiating point of a new business venture through business conceptualization. Furthermore, Varadarajan (2020) emphasized that knowledge in marketing is also a fundamental facet of starting a business because customer information is based on the Firm's resource-based, capabilities-based, and knowledge-based views. Thus, human resource management strategies are one of the most effective ways to maximize internal capital and increase profits by improving employee efficiency (Singh, Mondal, & Das, 2020).

Table 1. Level of the Respondents' Entrepreneurial Knowledge (n=140)

Constructs	Mean	SD Interpretation
Knowledge of Starting Business	3.00	0.35
Knowledge of Finance/Marketing	3.24	Satisfactory
Knowledge of Human Resource	3.28	0.48
Overall Entrepreneurial Knowledge	3.17	Satisfactory
		0.45
		Satisfactory
		0.15
		Satisfactory

Note: 3.25-4.00 Very Satisfactory (VS); 2.50-3.24 Satisfactory (S); 1.75-2.49 Fair (F); 1.00-1.74 Poor (P)

The graduates possess satisfactory knowledge of entrepreneurship. They can expand their entrepreneurial expertise by applying and learning new business principles. In this vein, the institution needs to examine the curriculum for the Business Administration program that encourages entrepreneurship through creative and practical experiential learning techniques to increase the level of the entrepreneurial knowledge of students. The learning institution encourages more active learning, internships, fieldwork, and the creation of a student-run mini-business to impact students' competencies, values, and beliefs.

B. The Level of the Respondents' Entrepreneurial Skills

Table 2 presents the level of the respondents' entrepreneurial skills. It is indicated that the respondents have good entrepreneurial skills (M=3.09; SD=0.07), as supported by all constructs included, such as technical skills (M=3.09; SD=0.54), managerial skills (M=3.11; SD=0.49), business skills (M=3.00; SD=0.52) and personal-entrepreneurial skills (M=3.17; SD=.053). The finding implies that the graduates possess skills necessary for them as entrepreneurs.

The technical skills pertaining to the entrepreneurs' know-how should include oral and written communication skills. Entrepreneurs can create network building and coaching and demonstrate business management abilities such as systematic planning, goal setting, decision-making, control, negotiating, and capabilities in the fundamental functional areas of marketing and finance. In addition, entrepreneurs must be skilled at developing personal entrepreneurial qualities such as self-control, risk-taking, inventiveness, perseverance, leadership, and change orientation.

Entrepreneurial skills include management skills in business and people that will aid in the successful management of the business endeavor (Wickham, 2016). Furthermore, skills such as strategy, planning, marketing, finance, project, and time management are all part of the general management business abilities. Leadership, motivation, delegating, communication, and negotiation are examples of people management abilities that are vital in running a business effectively and efficiently (Hirsch et al., 2015).

Findings showed that the graduates' entrepreneurial skills are useful to entrepreneurs as they start and grow their businesses. However, the identified skills both were perceived overall importance and perceived usefulness. This indicates that respondents have latent skills that they are undervaluing. Thus, there is a need to bolster their skills in financial, business concepts, and environmental scanning through training and related processes.

Considering the study's findings, business administration students continuously expose themselves to avenues that will allow them to apply the entrepreneurial skills needed to succeed in their fields. The present curricular program of the BSBA needs to be reviewed to strengthen activities designed to simulate actual-world situations. Students also need to undergo ocular visits to small-medium enterprises, forums or symposia, and trade fairs to develop real-life entrepreneurial skills. The business program needs to materialize the entrepreneurship-related student activities and develop the importance of entrepreneurship competencies to have interesting activities to encourage serious intentions to establish and run their own business.

Table 2. Respondents' Level of Entrepreneurial Skills (N=140)

Constructs	Mean	SD Interpretation
Technical Skills	3.09	0.54
Managerial Skills	3.11	Satisfactory
Business Skills	3.00	0.49
Personal-Entrepreneurial Skills	3.17	Satisfactory
		0.52
		Satisfactory
		0.53
		Satisfactory

Overall Entrepreneurial Skills	3.09
0.07	Satisfactory

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Satisfactory (VS); 2.50-3.24 Satisfactory (S); 1.75-2.49 Fair (F) 1.00-1.74 Poor (P)

C. Level of the Respondents' Perceived Entrepreneurial Performance

Table 3 shows the respondents' entrepreneurial performance is very good (M=3.35; SD=1.04). The finding implies that the graduates claimed to have very competent and competitive skills making them able to succeed in their chosen field. Their satisfactory knowledge and skills have made them capable of achieving successful entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurial activity depends largely on how graduates perceive the feasibility of the undertaking based on the desirability of the activity in the social context and perceived support. Studies have pointed out that graduates are more willing to consider becoming entrepreneurs if they know about the various support mechanisms. Financial risks were one of the important barriers to starting a company. The overall abilities in managing a business as to financial ratio projection, growth, and competitive edge positively impact successful ventures. They stressed that their growing financial ratio could help their business become stable and lead them to become satisfied in their respective practices within their territorial scope. Business growth and profitability are common indicators of a company's financial health, even if they can sometimes produce a trade-off. This supports the claim of Zahra (2016) that firms may spend extensively on long-term growth at the expense of short-term profitability. Sales, earnings, employment, and market share are all indicators of firm growth. In contrast, profitability indicators include accounting-based metrics like return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and return on sales (ROS) (Rauch et al., 2019).

Table 3. Respondents' Entrepreneurial Performance (n=140)

Constructs	Mean	SD Interpretation
Financial Ratio as to:		
Degree of Importance	2.73	0.34 Good
Degree of Satisfaction	2.58	0.42 Good
Growth of the Firm	4.77	0.80 Very
Performance Relative to Competitors	3.97	Good
		0.75 Very
		Good
Overall Weighted Mean		3.35
	1.04	Very Good

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Good (VG); 2.50-3.24 Good (G); 1.75-2.49 Poor (P) 1.00-1.74 Very Poor (VP)

It is widely accepted that entrepreneurial education is as much about honing broad creative and entrepreneurial abilities as it is about improving company success. Entrepreneurial education helps people develop the entrepreneurial skills needed to run a firm successfully. Such education also aids in gaining confidence in their ability (Minai et al., 2018).

The Business Administration program aims to produce graduates who will become skilled, flexible, and adaptable entrepreneurs to the challenging needs of the business world (CBM College Catalogue, 2020). The program particularly aims this by reflecting on the learning outcomes such as planning and implementing business-related activities, innovating business ideas based on emerging industries, and analyzing the business environment for strategic direction. These related program learning outcomes (PLO) of the Business Administration are realized through the graduates' performance. Graduates provide evidence of achieving the program learning outcomes through their entrepreneurial achievement. Entrepreneurs always search for the best opportunities for the betterment of their firms.

D. Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Entrepreneurial Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Performance

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between respondents' entrepreneurial knowledge on starting a business, finance and marketing, and the human resource to the respondents' entrepreneurial performance as to financial ratio, growth of the Firm, and relative to competitors. It is shown in the table that the knowledge on starting a business and financial ratio as to the degree of importance and satisfaction have opposite results with no significant relationship and with significant relationship (r-value= 0.03; p-value= 0.72) and (r-

value = 0.18; p-value = 0.02) respectively. Similarly, the knowledge of financial and marketing and financial ratio as to the degree of importance and satisfaction show opposite results of having no significant relationship (r-value = 0.17; p-value = 0.34) and (r-value = 0.23; p-value = 0.00), respectively. The knowledge of human resource and financial ratio as to the degree of importance and satisfaction shows a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.25; p-value = 0.00) and (r-value = 0.28; P value = 0.00), respectively. However, the knowledge of starting a business and the Firm's growth show a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.33; p-value = 0.00). More so, the Firm's knowledge of financial and marketing and growth shows a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.21; p-value = 0.01).

Similarly, the knowledge of human resources, the Firm's growth, the knowledge of starting a business, and performance relative to the competitors show a highly significant relationship (r-value= 0.25; p-value = 0.00). The knowledge of finance, marketing, and performance relative to competitors shows a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.23; p-value 0.00). The knowledge of human resources and performance relative to competitors show a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.13; p-value = 0.01).

The findings imply that the knowledge of starting a business, finance, marketing, and human resource affect the respondents' performance as to financial ratio, growth of the Firm, and relative to competitors. The entrepreneurial knowledge of the respondents can impact their respective performance in operating their businesses and the business industry. Entrepreneurs choose a business venture and consider their passion in choosing what they want to focus on while considering the feasibility of a business idea.

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Entrepreneurial Knowledge and Performance (n=140)

Variables	Test Statistics		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Knowledge of Starting a Business and Financial Ratio as to: Degree of Importance Degree of Satisfaction	0.03	0.72	Not Significant Significant
	0.18	0.02*	
Knowledge of Finance and Marketing and Financial Ratios as to: Degree of Importance Degree of Satisfaction	0.17	0.34	Not Significant Highly Significant
	0.23	0.00**	
Knowledge of Human Resource and Financial Ratios as to: Degree of Importance Degree of Satisfaction	0.25	0.00**	Highly Significant Highly Significant
	0.28	0.00**	
Knowledge of Starting a Business and Growth of the Firm	0.33	0.00**	Highly Significant
Knowledge of Finance and Marketing and Growth of the Firm	0.21	0.01**	Highly Significant
Knowledge of Human Resource and Growth of the Firm	0.25	0.00**	Highly Significant

Knowledge of Starting a Business and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.25	0.00**	Highly Significant
Knowledge of Finance and Marketing and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.23	0.00**	Highly Significant
Knowledge of Human Resource and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.13	0.01**	Highly Significant

*Legend: 0.00-0.01** Highly Significant 0.02-0.05*Significant More than 0.05 Not Significant*

An entrepreneur who has adequate knowledge in the three areas (starting a business, financial and marketing, and human resource) can help them to be confident in several strategies like managing their marketing campaigns, their financial position, and stability as well as the degree in managing their people within their business activities. Functional areas will impact managing their businesses (Roxasa, 2013). Moreover, this knowledge can help entrepreneurs to create strategic forces toward their rival competitors. Entrepreneurs must assess the internal and external factors that would affect the business's long-term success by adapting appropriate business strategies in managing the business activity that would create a healthy competitive environment (Dobrović & Furjan, 2020). Knowledge is usually seen as a requisite for voluntary action and an essential predictor. Entrepreneurial knowledge lies at the heart of entrepreneurship and substantially impacts venture development decisions and intentions (Yaghoubi, Karimi, & Motaghd, 2017).

Higher education and courses are designed to provide students with a foundation of knowledge and encourage them to think entrepreneurially. Therefore, graduate surveys can give useful statistics for evaluating educational and training outcomes and serve as the foundation for future planning activities such as curriculum review and re-engineering of topic content or program development to suit global demands (Dulnuan, 2016). In addition, the implications of the result of this study can be utilized as the foundation for future curriculum modification, which is a critical step toward program improvement.

The Business Administration program continues to develop through initiative, creativity, problem-solving, and class-based discussions of case studies or hypothetical questions related to entrepreneurship that may help graduates become successful entrepreneurs in the future. Students need out-of-the-box information to enhance knowledge independent

of context and not only communicated through books, manuals, and training.

E. Significant Relationship between Respondents' Entrepreneurial Skills and performance

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' entrepreneurial skills and performance (Table 5). It is indicated that the relationship between respondents' entrepreneurial skills and performance is highly significant. The technical skills and financial ratio show a highly significant relationship between the degree of importance (r-value = 0.30; p-value = 0.00). The technical skills and financial ratio in relation to the degree of satisfaction show a highly significant result (r-value = 0.25; p-value = 0.00). Managerial skills and financial ratio show a highly significant result regarding the degree of importance and satisfaction (r-value = 0.37; p-value = 0.00). Finally, the business skills and financial ratio regarding the degree of importance shows a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.23; p-value = 0.00).

Meanwhile, the business skills and financial ratio about the degree of satisfaction show a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.36; p-value = 0.00). Likewise, the personal-entrepreneurial skills and financial ratio about the degree of importance show a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.39; p-value = 0.00). However, on the other hand, the personal entrepreneurial skills and the financial ratio of the degree of satisfaction show a highly significant relationship (r-value = 0.38; p-value = 0.00).

The findings imply that the respondents' entrepreneurial skills impact their performance; therefore, real entrepreneurial skills are attributed to the entrepreneurs' know-how in establishing and operating their businesses successfully. More so, entrepreneurial skills are considered the unique capabilities of an entrepreneur to help the organization gain a long-term advantage.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Entrepreneurial Skills and Performance (n=140)

Variables	Test Statistics		Remarks
	r value	p-value	
Technical Skills and Financial Ratio as to:			
Degree of Importance	0.30	0.00**	Highly Significant
Degree of Satisfaction	0.25	0.00**	Highly Significant
Managerial Skills and Financial Ratio as to:			
Degree of Importance	0.37	0.00**	Highly Significant
Degree of Satisfaction	0.37	0.00**	Highly Significant

Business Skills and Financial Ratio as to:			
Degree of Importance	0.23	0.00**	Highly Significant
Degree of Satisfaction	0.36	0.00**	Highly Significant
Personal Entrepreneurial Skills and Financial Ratio as to:			
Degree of Importance	0.39	0.00**	Highly Significant
Degree of Satisfaction	0.38	0.00**	Highly Significant
Technical Skills and Growth of the Firm	0.32	0.00**	Highly Significant
Managerial Skills and Growth of the Firm	0.437	0.00**	Highly Significant
Business Skills and Growth of the Firm	0.36	0.00**	Highly Significant
Personal Entrepreneurial Skills and Growth of the Firm	0.48	0.00**	Highly Significant
Technical Skills and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.32	0.00**	Highly Significant
Managerial Skills and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.36	0.00**	Highly Significant
Business Skills and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.36	0.00**	Highly Significant
Personal Entrepreneurial Skills and Performance Relative to Competitors	0.46	0.00**	Highly Significant

*Legend: 0.00-0.01** Highly Significant 0.02-0.05*Significant More than 0.05 Not Significant*

It has been found that entrepreneurial skills are an important resource that can lead to a firm's long-term competitive advantage or affect a firm's growth. Entrepreneurship education has a positive and statistically relevant relationship with the need for accomplishment, risk-taking tendency, internal locus of influence, and entrepreneurial target intentions among business graduates (Al Mamun, Fazal, & Muniady, 2019). Furthermore, entrepreneurial skills are part of a set of generic talents that can assist entrepreneurs in thinking critically in a real-world business setting while making sound judgments in the face of complicated difficulties (Kristinae, Wardana, Giantari, & Rahyuda, 2020).

Business Administration graduates who are future entrepreneurs better acquire twenty-first-century entrepreneurial skills combined with technical skills through the business curriculum. These twenty-first-century skills include communication, decision-making, collaboration, problem-solving, understanding customer needs, planning, and management experience (Ansari et al., 2014; Boyles, 2012; Neck, Greene, & Brush, 2014; Sumedrea, 2015). Specifically, entrepreneurship skills include working up a concept into a business plan, opportunity recognition, environmental scanning, and access to external expertise. Learning to be an entrepreneur is best accomplished by “doing” and gaining experience in real-world scenarios through collaboration with actual businesspeople. It is the challenge of entrepreneurship education today to develop strategies to help students develop these skills and be better prepared to become entrepreneurs who will succeed and thrive.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The government sector and academic community have given the value of entrepreneurship importance. Business Administration graduates require entrepreneurial knowledge and skills to prepare to handle risk and successfully manage ventures after graduation. Their satisfactory entrepreneurial knowledge and skills contribute to good performance in entrepreneurial ventures. The graduates' knowledge of starting a business, finance, marketing, and human resource, as well as the technical, managerial, business, and personal entrepreneurial skills, impact their performance as entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial knowledge and skills influence the entrepreneurial performance of graduates.

Based on the findings and conclusions, it is recommended that business educators primarily designed to provide training to would-be entrepreneurs in starting and operating a business as well as building one's character. The promotion of real-life activities is relevant to the graduates' entrepreneurial competencies. The Business Administration students are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills in identifying business opportunities, business planning, financing, company valuation, and business management. The twenty-first-century entrepreneurial skills serve as a guide for developing competitive graduates. The business sectors and academic business council create partnerships to create a strong foundation for graduates' employment. Future researchers will study how the community promotes entrepreneurial engagement among business graduates.

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